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ANALYSIS OF THE STATE AND PROSPECTS OF LTE TECHNOLOGY IN THE INTRODUCTION OF THE INTERNET OF THINGS

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Abstract

In the coming years, LTE technology will develop at the fastest pace and will probably be the main option for wireless data transmission of the Internet of Things (IoT) over cellular networks. With the development of 5G networks and the Internet of Things (IoT) of the fifth generation, many new services will appear for people and society as a whole, and the growth of the 5G technology network segment will contribute to business development in all sectors. Nb-IoT is a specification of the cellular standard, which is designed to service devices that generate small amounts of data. The technology is excellent for various meters, sensors, alarm systems, etc. This article is devoted to the analysis of the state and prospects of the application of LTE technology in the introduction of the Internet of Things.

Keywords: 4G, LTE, 5G, Internet of Things (IoT), Narrow-Band IoT, mobile network.

Introduction

4G is the fourth generation of mobile communications. The formal date for the emergence of 4G was 2008, when the International Telecommunication Union set standards for it. According to these standards, the connection speed for moving objects (smartphones, tablets) must be at least 100 Mbps, and for static (access points) - at least 1 Gbps.

Over the next few years, companies worked to bring these speeds closer. That's how LTE (Long Term EVolution) came about - a new communication standard that was originally positioned as an improved 3G.

However, the International Telecommunication Union has decided that the LTE standard can be described as 4G if it offers significant improvements over the previous generation of communications. Companies immediately began to advertise their connection as 4G LTE, using marketing tricks that allowed them to talk about the "new generation" and without reaching its standards.

The standard that can really be considered true 4G is called LTE Advanced (LTE-A). In 2012, it was officially recognized by the same International Telecommunication Union. LTE Advanced meets all the requirements of 4G, in particular, meets the speed.

However, it is important to note that communication in devices connected to LTE-A can only theoretically reach the required 100 Mbps and 1 Gbps, ie such speeds a smartphone with LTE-A can reach only in the laboratory.

According to the results of 2020, 4.5 billion connections in the global LTE networks are 57% of all mobile connections. By the end of this year, 4G networks will cover 80% of the world's population, and in 2026 - 95%. The demand for LTE will peak in 2021, when the number of connections will reach 4.8 billion, and then the demand for LTE services will begin to decline gradually and by the end of 2026 will be only 3.9 billion connections. The reason is obvious - the migration of subscribers to 5G technology.

* The number of users of fixed broadband Internet (FDI) is at least three times less than the number of connections to these networks. The opposite is true with mobile phones - the number of connections is greater than the number of users. Connections to fixed-wireless networks were not taken into account when estimating the number of connections to fixed-line networks.

Fig.1. Connections and users (billion)

For the mobile market, 2020 has been the year of fifth generation (5G) technology - the number of commercial networks has exceeded 100, and by the end of the year in their coverage area will live 15% of the world's population. It is already clear that 5G will be the fastest growing technology, which will significantly

exceed the standards of previous generations. By the end of the year, operators will have 220 million 5G connections, and in 2026 - 3.5 billion. New scenarios are being created that use the key advantages of 5G technologies: low latency, high speed and reliable protection of transmitted data.

Fig.2. Dynamics of growth of connections in 5G and 4G networks during the first years (billion). Source: Ericsson Mobility Report November 2020[1,2].

According to reputable research centers, in the coming years, LTE technology will develop at the fastest pace and will probably be the main option for wireless data transmission "Internet of Things" (IoT) over cellular networks.

With the development of 5G networks, usage scenarios based on critical Internet of Things (CriticalIoT) connections will become widespread. With the development of 5G networks and the Internet of Things (IoT)

of the fifth generation, many new services will appear for people and society as a whole, and the growth of the 5G technology network segment will contribute to business development in all sectors. Data transfer for a guaranteed period of time - for example, 50 milliseconds with a 99.9% guarantee - will be required for applications designed to control devices remotely, as well as for entertainment services.

Experts have identified [2] four types of promising scenarios for the use of 5G technologies, which require connection to a network with guaranteed data transmission time.

1. Real-time media technology - connections in which data transmission time plays a key role. They allow you to create industrial applications and cloud gaming services using augmented and virtual reality (AR / VR) technologies.

2. Remote control devices - a person remotely controls machines and equipment moving on land and air. People will no longer have to work in difficult climatic and dangerous conditions - instead they will control autonomous devices.

3. Industrial control - real-time monitoring and control functions will be used to control smart grids, and machine vision technology will be available for robots.

4. Mobile automation - automation of the cycle of control of vehicles and mobile works will provide safe maneuvering of many remotely controlled devices on one site.

Fifth generation networks will allow you to combine all the devices of a smart home into a single high-speed system. Counters, door locks, game and TV set-top boxes, climate control and security systems - all this can be connected via a mobile network to a single control device.

5G is able to combine the devices of an entire smart city. Traffic lights, surveillance cameras, bank terminals, parking meters, car navigators, rented vehicles (including unmanned) - smart devices in real time will exchange information with each other. Owners of gadgets connected to 5G will experience unprecedented freedom of interaction with each other. You will have almost instant access to cloud services, streaming video, multiplayer cloud games, augmented and virtual reality shopping, online remote collaboration and more.

With the development of the Internet of Things (IoT), the number of connections to mobile networks of operators will increase many times. According to Ericsson [4], by 2021 the total number of devices connected to the Internet in the world will be 28 billion, of which 1.5 billion will be consumer electronics and smart cars that interact with each other through mobile networks. In the coming years, the number of machine-to-machine (M2M) connections will grow by 25% per year, and most M2M devices available on the market will support the LTE standard. As the IoT market grows, it is becoming apparent that for many applications, existing mobile technologies are inadequate due to insufficient coverage, high cost of end terminals, and short life of their batteries.

An innovative solution for the Internet of Things - Narrow-Band IoT

Innovative Internet of Things technology is a Narrow-Band IoT (NB-IoT) solution. It is a wireless low-bandwidth version of the Low Power Wide Area (LPWA), which is primarily designed for inter-machine interoperability (M2M) applications. The NB-IoT standard will open up a wide range of new opportunities for companies specializing in telecommunications services. In particular, it will significantly increase the profitability of operators per subscriber (Average revenue per user, ARPU). NB-IoT technology will occupy its low-speed niche in the class of solutions, where the priority is uninterrupted data transmission and low power consumption.

In early 2020, Vodafone Ukraine launched the Nb-IoT network, which is a dedicated frequency channel for IoT equipment in the existing LTE network [5].

Nb-IoT is a specification of the cellular standard, which is designed to service devices that generate small amounts of data. The technology is perfect for various meters, sensors, alarm systems, etc.

In terms of its physical structure and architecture, the Nb-IoT network inherited almost everything from LTE, so building an Internet of Things infrastructure requires nothing more than updating software on existing base stations. Due to the simplicity of the system, operators can provide low rates for customers of the Internet of Things.

The main characteristics of Nb-IoT

- Sufficient bandwidth for most IoT devices.
- You can exchange objects spaced in time.
- Ability to work in more remote areas than 4G on the same frequency.
- Noise resistance.
- Incredibly low power consumption (sensors can "live" from one battery for about 10 years).
- Reduced CPU requirements.

To understand how these properties are achieved, it is necessary to delve a little deeper into the technical component of the network.

Nb-IoT is based on LTE. In simple terms, the 4G band consists of separate channels (subcarriers) of 15 kHz. The carrier in LTE is divided into resource blocks (RB), each of which consists of 12 subcarriers of 15 kHz. A total of 180 kHz is obtained. Each resource block includes 84 resource elements (12 by 7 grid). The 5 MHz band, which can run LTE, includes 25 resource blocks.

Fig. 3. Component of the Nb-IoT network

Only one 180 kHz resource unit is used to run Nb-IoT. For signal range it is amplified by 6 dB. This explains why the Internet of Things has a wider coverage than LTE, although the frequency used is the same.

Network startup can be done in three ways:

1. on a dedicated 200 kHz channel, which also includes a protection spectrum of 300-600 kHz to avoid interference. This method is not relevant for Ukraine, as the frequency resource is not enough, plus you need more costs;

2. on the guard band: each band on which the operators deploy the communication has a guard interval of 500 kHz on each side. This option is suitable if you want to save frequency resource and reduce the mutual impact on the LTE network;
3. inside the strip (relevant for Ukraine).

Nb-IoT technology is considered to be the transition to the fifth generation of communication

Fig. 4. Ways to lowering Nb-IoT network

Maximum speeds in the Nb-IoT network

For different sensors, the speed does not matter much: the stability of the connection is much more important. It is worth noting that one device can not occupy all available radio resources, so customers do not have problems with the connection.

The data transfer rate in Nb-IoT reaches 58.8 Kbps. There are solutions that can increase this value to a maximum of 100 Kbps.

Data transmission on the 15 kHz subcarrier allows to increase the spectral density of the signal, thereby reducing the signal-to-noise ratio. Noise reduction is especially important for IoT devices because they have weak transmitters.

Features of energy consumption in the Nb-IoT network

Low energy consumption is achieved not only due to low data rates, but also by reducing the number of energy-intensive registration procedures in the network. When turned on, each device communicates with the base station, "agrees" on the mode of operation and then "falls asleep". In case of awakening, the data can be transferred immediately. In sleep mode, the base station is a gateway and accumulates information for the end device. This reduces the time on the radio. It is important to note that for such work the equipment must be at one point. Moving the device forces each time to "discuss" with the base station such parameters as power, sensitivity, etc.

Conclusions

A study by the World Bank and the Swedish School of Economics on the impact of broadband access on the economy shows that with a 10% increase in Broadband penetration, the economy gains an additional 1-2% of GDP. This applies to developed countries. For developing economies, as in Ukraine, the impact is even greater. Society will strive to automate everyday tasks. The pandemic has shown that migration to digital technologies will accelerate. One example of the

impact of the mobile Internet on people's lives is the 2020 quarantine.

Internet of Things (IoT) -based technologies will be the most promising. Industrial IoT solutions allow more efficient use of enterprise resources and minimize production losses. Experience shows that thanks to this technology companies can save 17-20% of operating costs [6]. Businesses don't have to wait for 5G to start implementing new technologies. 4G and other communication standards in Ukraine are already successfully meeting most of the needs of large, small and medium enterprises.

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